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A Case of Autism Spectrum Disorder Treated with Homoeopathic Medicines

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ABSTRACT

Autism spectrum disorder is a Neurological Condition characterized by differences in social interaction, Communication and behavior. It affects individuals to Varying degree with unique Strengths and Challenges. In recent times, there has been a surge in prevalence of ASD. While the causes of ASD remain unknown. It is believed that a faulty placenta, premature birth, encephalitis and-toxic environment may be Contributing factors. ASD required specific therapies of behavior intervention for treatment. Homeopathy, with its comprehensive approach, has been found to be effective in reducing the Severity of autistic symptoms. This study present a case of ASD that improved significantly with the administration of medics Homoeopathic medicines High lighten the potential benefits of Homoeopathy in treating ASD. To evaluate the off efficacy of Homoeopathic management in managing ASD

Keywords: Autism spectrum disorder, Neurological Condition, Homoeopathic medicines

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INTRODUCTION

A 7 yrs. old boy Paras diagnosed with ASD 2 yrs. ago presented ASD presented with such symptoms.

- Delayed speech, Dumbness in Behavior.
- Hyperactive and slow learning.
- No eye contact
- Sleeplessness
- Enuresis without dreams.
- Anger, Sudden repulsive Behavior, specially towards Himself, Hit Himself sometimes.
- Aloofness

Medicines Prescribed

- Aethusa -200-BD
- Tarantula His-30-TDS
- Tuberculinum-200 once in a week.

Results: after administration of above-mentioned medicines Follow up done after one month.

The Key Changes in patient was.

- Child becomes calm Comparatively previous month.
- Better Enuresis. Child had tendency to urinate every night which remains 2-3 times in a month.
- Eye Contact improved
- Better sleep

AGAIN, REPEAT SAME MEDICINE FOR ANOTHER 30 DAYS

In Next follow up key changes were.

- No Bed wetting.
- Learning became better but speech delayed
- Irritability, Anger has been reduced.
- For Next follow up medicines were prescribed
Baryta Carb-200 BD
- Aethusa-1M-one dose Repeat after 15 days. Follow up after 30 days
- Speech becomes better child tries to learn new words.
- According to child parents now he can sit in the class for long time as compared to previous time.

Child symptoms gradually improved and he is currently undergoing treatment.

RESULTS:

Homeopathic treatment for ASD promising trend with many cases being successfully treated and even cured. This Case demonstrated marked improvement in the signs of symptoms and its severity
Review Given by child parents by

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